

Kruppel like factor 4 (KLF4/EZF/GKLF) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : KLF4 is a member of the KLF family of zinc finger transcription factors, which belongs to the relatively large family of SP1-like transcription factors and has been proven necessary for both induction and maintenance of pluripotency and self-renewal. Unique mutation in KLF4 (i.e KLF4^{K409Q}) in human meningiomas have been found to change the evolutionarily conserved DNA-binding domain of KLF4, thus altering its DNA recognition preference and resulting in a shift in downstream transcriptional activity. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of KLF4, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

*ML dicoveries of KLF4 synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there

exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Kruppel like factor 4 (KLF4/EZF/GKLF)

The Kruppel-like family of transcription factors are a set of eukaryotic C2H2 zinc finger DNA-binding proteins that regulate gene expression. Zinc finger transcription factors or ZF-TFs, are composed of a zinc finger-DNA-binding domains (Gommans et al. [13]).

A zinc finger is a small protein structural motif that contains one or more zinc ions (Zn^{2+}) which stabilizes the fold. For the first time, Hanas et al. [14] found that transcription factor A from immature *Xenopus* oocytes was associated with 5 S RNA in

a 7 S nucleoprotein complex and the atomic absorption analysis of EDTA-dialyzed 7 S particles revealed 2 mol of zinc/mol of particle. It was observed that factor A obtained from EDTA-dialyzed particles bound to the 5 S RNA gene as determined by DNase I footprinting and factor A alone, obtained by RNase digestion of the 7 S particle, contained zinc, when dialyzed in the absence of EDTA.

Shields et al. [15] isolated a cDNA clone from an NIH 3T3 library using a probe encoding the zinc finger region of the immediate-early transcription factor *zif/268* and named it gut-enriched Kruppel-like factor (GKLF). They observed that the deduced GKLF amino acid sequence contained three tandem zinc fingers that were related to members of the Kruppel family of transcription factors. By indirect immunofluorescence, they found that GKLF is localized to the cell nucleus. In cultured fibroblasts, GKLF mRNA was found in high levels in growth-arrested cells and was nearly undetectable in cells that are in the exponential phase of proliferation, while *In situ* hybridization experiments indicated that GKLF mRNA was enriched in epithelial cells located in the middle to upper crypt region of the colonic mucosa. Taken together, their results suggested that GKLF was potentially a negative regulator of cell growth in tissues such as the gut mucosa, where cell proliferation was coupled to growth arrest and differentiation.

Further, Garrett-Sinha et al. [16] identified a novel zinc-finger protein whose mRNA was expressed at high levels in the epidermal layer of the skin and in epithelial cells in the tongue, palate, esophagus, stomach, and colon of newborn mice. They observed that the carboxyl terminus of the protein contained three zinc fingers with a high degree of homology to erythroid Kruppel-like factor and bound to DNA fragments containing CACCC motifs. The amino-terminal portion of the protein was proline and serine-rich and could function as a transcriptional activator. Using mouse interspecific backcrosses, they mapped the chromosomal location of the gene and showed that it localized to mouse chromosome 4 and to cosegregate with the thioredoxin gene.

Using a DNA probe from the zinc finger region of erythroid Kruppel-like factor (EKLF), Yet et al. [17] cloned a cDNA encoding a member of this multigene family (which contained three C-terminal zinc fingers) from a human vascular endothelial cell cDNA library. Sequence analysis indicated that their clone, hEZF, was the human homologue of the recently reported mouse EZF and GKLF and was a single-copy gene that mapped to chromosome 9q31. By gel mobility shift analysis, they found that purified recombinant hEZF protein bound specifically to a probe containing the CACCC core sequence. By fusing hEZF to the DNA-binding domain of GAL4, they mapped a repression domain in hEZF to amino acids 181-388 and also found that amino acids 91-117 of hEZF conferred an activation function on the GAL4 DNA-binding domain. EKLF transactivated the beta-globin promoter by binding to the CACCC motif and was essential for expression of the beta-globin gene as demonstrated by gene deletion experiments in mice.

The secretory variant of meningioma are characterized by glandular differentiation, formation of intracellular lumina and pseudopsammoma bodies, expression of a distinct pattern of cytokeratins and clinically by pronounced perifocal brain edema. Reuss et al. [18] described whole-exome sequencing analysis of DNA from 16 secretory meningiomas and corresponding constitutional tissues and found that all of them invariably harbored a mutation in both KLF4 and TRAF7. Further, it was observed

that all KLF4 mutations were identical, affected codon 409 and resulted in a lysine to glutamine exchange (K409Q). Also, KLF4 and TRAF7 mutations were found to be mutually exclusive with NF2 mutations. In conclusion, their findings suggested an essential contribution of combined KLF4 K409Q and TRAF7 mutations in the genesis of secretory meningioma and demonstrated a role for TRAF7 alterations in other non-NF2 meningiomas.

Tang et al. [19] successfully isolated stem-like cells from human anaplastic meningioma which are capable of forming spheres and initiating xenograft tumors that recapitulate anaplastic meningioma phenotypes, and thus could serve as an *in vitro* model for malignant meningiomas. KLF4, a transcription factor known for its role in stemness maintenance, was identified as one of the most frequently mutated genes in the benign secretory meningioma. They found that KLF4 was downregulated in anaplastic meningioma compared with low-grade meningioma subtypes. By manipulating KLF4 expression in anaplastic meningioma stem-like cells, they demonstrated that KLF4 acted as a tumor suppressor during malignant progression in meningioma, affecting apoptosis, proliferation, invasion, and cell cycle. Their results suggested a potential therapeutic value of KLF4 for clinical intervention of anaplastic meningioma.

von Spreckelsen et al. [20] reported that the KLF4-K409Q mutation in skull base meningiomas triggered a distinct tumor phenotype. Their transcriptomic analysis of 17 meningioma samples revealed that KLF4^{K409Q} mutated tumors harbored an upregulation of hypoxia dependent pathways, as detailed in *in vitro* investigation confirmed that the KLF4^{K409Q} mutation induced HIF-1 α through the reduction of prolyl hydroxylase activity and caused an upregulation of downstream HIF-1 α targets. Finally, they also demonstrated that KLF4^{K409Q} mutated tumors were susceptible to mTOR inhibition by Temsirolimus.

Using genome-wide high-throughput and focused quantitative transcriptional approaches in human cell lines, primary meningeal cells, and meningioma tumor tissue, Tsytsykova et al. [21] found that a change in the evolutionarily conserved DNA-binding domain of KLF4 altered its DNA recognition preference, thus resulting in a shift in downstream transcriptional activity. In the KLF4^{K409Q}-specific targets, the normally silent fibroblast growth factor 3 (FGF3) was found to be activated and they further demonstrated a neomorphic function of KLF4^{K409Q} in stimulating FGF3 transcription through binding to its promoter and in using short tandem repeats (STRs) located within the locus as enhancers.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however,

vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [22] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [23] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [23].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette

scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [24]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [25], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [22] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [22]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [26], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. KLF4 related synergies

Note - KLF4 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2^{nd} order combinations of KLF4 were recorded.

3.1.1. KLF4^{K409Q} vs GFP activated genes

Tsytysykova et al. [21] recorded 141 differentially expressed genes activated by KLF4^{K409Q}. Of these, erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 3 (ERBB3), RAP1 GTPase activating protein (RAP1GAP), tight junction protein 3 (TJP3), FXYD domain containing ion transport regulator 6 (FXYD6) and forkhead box I2 (FOXI2), were found to be recorded as up-regulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of KLF4 with these genes.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t KLF4. FXYD6 - KLF4 shows high ranking of 251 (laplace), 281 (linear), 280 (rbf) and 274 (jansen) and FOXI2 - KLF4 shows high ranking of 291 (laplace), 299 (linear), 259 (rbf) and 279 (jansen); while ERBB3 - KLF4 shows low ranking of 18, 49, 38 and 263; RAP1GAP - KLF4 shows low ranking of 75, 52, 44 and 260 and TJP3 - KLF4 shows low ranking of 59, 48, 20 and 276.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS IN KLF4 ^{K409Q} VS KLF4				
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS IN KLF4 ^{K409Q} W.R.T KLF4				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ERBB3 - KLF4	18	49	38	263
RAP1GAP - KLF4	75	52	44	260
TJP3 - KLF4	59	48	20	276
FXYD6 - KLF4	251	281	280	274
FOXI2 - KLF4	291	299	259	279

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between KLF4 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t KLF4 with KLF4 – > FXYD6 / FOXI2.

3.1.2. KLF4^{WT} vs GFP activated genes

Tsytysykova et al. [21] recorded 116 differentially expressed genes activated by KLF4^{WT}. Of these, immunoglobulin superfamily member 9 (IGSF9), parathyroid hormone like

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t KLF4	
FXVD6	KLF4
FOXI2	KLF4

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between KLF4 and Individual members.

hormone (PTHLH), fms related receptor tyrosine kinase 1 (FLT1), periplakin (PPL), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 9 (TTC9), atypical chemokine receptor 3 (ACKR3), lipocalin 2 (LCN2), C3 and PZP like alpha-2-macroglobulin domain containing 8 (CPAMD8) and mucin 3A, cell surface associated (MUC3A), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of KLF4 with these genes.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t KLF4. ACKR3 - KLF4 shows high ranking of 154 (laplace), 290 (linear), 256 (rbf) and 188 (jansen); LCN2 - KLF4 shows high ranking of 243 (laplace), 258 (linear), 220 (rbf) and 136 (jansen); CPAMD8 - KLF4 shows high ranking of 220 (laplace), 233 (linear), 230 (rbf) and 153 (jansen); and MUC3A - KLF4 shows high ranking of 304 (laplace), 276 (linear), 285 (rbf) and 284 (jansen); while IGSF9 - KLF4 shows low ranking of 74, 72, 17 and 129; PTHLH - KLF4 shows low ranking of 8, 29, 68 and 234; FLT1 - KLF4 shows low ranking of 95, 51, 104 and 2; PPL - KLF4 shows low ranking of 31, 65, 59 and 187; and TTC9 - KLF4 shows low ranking of 205, 85, 102 and 67.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t KLF4 with KLF4 – > ACKR3 / LCN2 / CPAMD8 / MUC3A.

3.1.3. KLF4^{K409Q} vs GFP and KLF4^{WT} vs GFP activated genes

Tsytsykova et al. [21] recorded 74 differentially expressed genes activated by both KLF4^{WT} and KLF4^{K409Q}. Of these, USH1 protein network component harmonin (USH1C), calmodulin regulated spectrin associated protein family member 3 (CAM-SAP3), neurotensin receptor 1 (NTSR1), eukaryotic translation elongation factor 1 alpha 2 (EEF1A2), kallikrein related peptidase 10 (KLK10), shisa like 1 (KIAA1644), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6B2 (COX6B2) and keratin 16 (KRT16), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of KLF4 with these genes.

Table 5 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 6 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 5. The table 5 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t KLF4. KIAA1644 - KLF4 shows

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS IN KLF4 ^{WT} VS KLF4				
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS IN KLF4 ^{WT} W.R.T KLF4				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
IGSF9 - KLF4	74	72	17	129
PTHLH - KLF4	8	29	68	234
FLT1 - KLF4	95	51	104	2
PPL - KLF4	31	65	59	187
TTC9 - KLF4	205	85	102	67
ACKR3 - KLF4	154	290	256	188
LCN2 - KLF4	243	258	220	136
CPAMD8 - KLF4	220	233	230	153
MUC3A - KLF4	304	276	285	284

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between KLF4 VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t KLF4	
ACKR3	KLF4
LCN2	KLF4
CPAMD8	KLF4
MUC3A	KLF4

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between KLF4 and Individual members.

high ranking of 158, 218, 195 and 198; COX6B2 - KLF4 shows high ranking of 302, 292, 243 and 285 and KRT16 - KLF4 shows high ranking of 280, 243, 283 and 294; while USH1C - KLF4 shows low ranking of 27, 35, 8 and 267; CAMSAP3 - KLF4 shows low ranking of 126, 83, 49 and 201; NTSR1 - KLF4 shows low ranking of 23, 14, 2 and 255; EEF1A2 - KLF4 shows low ranking of 7, 47, 64 and 95; and KLK10 - KLF4 shows low ranking of 44, 2, 39 and 218.

One can also interpret the results of the table 5 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t KLF4 with KLF4 – > KIAA1644 / COX6B2 and KRT16.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS IN KLF4 ^{WT} & KLF4 ^{K409Q} VS KLF4				
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS IN KLF4 ^{WT} & KLF4 ^{K409Q} W.R.T KLF4				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
USH1C - KLF4	27	35	8	267
CAMSAP3 - KLF4	126	83	49	201
NTSR1 - KLF4	23	14	2	255
EEF1A2 - KLF4	7	47	64	95
KLK10 - KLF4	44	2	39	218
KIAA1644 - KLF4	158	218	195	198
COX6B2 - KLF4	302	292	243	285
KRT16 - KLF4	280	243	283	294

Table 5: 2nd order interaction ranking between KLF4 VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t KLF4	
KIAA1644	KLF4
COX6B2	KLF4
KRT16	KLF4

Table 6: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between KLF4 and Individual members.

3.1.4. KLF4 unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by KLF4, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [1]. i document here, the 2nd order combinations with KLF4, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the KLF4 and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

Of these, solute carrier family 7 member 8 (SLC7A8), afadin, adherens junction formation factor (AFDN), PILR alpha associated neural protein (PIANP), maelstrom spermatogenic transposon silencer (MAEL), tubulin alpha 4a (TUBA4A), HECT, C2 and WW domain containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 2 (HECW2), collagen type II alpha 1 chain (COL2A1), immunoglobulin like domain containing receptor 2 (ILDR2), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 13 (GALNT13), beta-1,4-mannosyl-glycoprotein 4-beta-N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase (MGAT3), cyclin dependent kinase like 2 (CDKL2), MAM domain containing glycosylphosphatidylinositol anchor 2 (MDGA2), sushi domain containing 4 (SUSD4), coiled-coil domain containing 150 (CCDC150), low density lipoprotein receptor (LDLR), epidermal growth factor (EGF), PR/SET domain 16 (PRDM16), HHIP like 2 (HHIPL2), atypical chemokine receptor 3 (ACKR3), ki-

nesin family member 21A (KIF21A), solute carrier family 44 member 3 (SLC44A3), thrombospondin type 1 domain containing 7B (THSD7B), glutamate decarboxylase like 1 (GADL1), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit beta2 (GABRB2), scavenger receptor cysteine rich family member with 4 domains (SSC4D), solute carrier family 26 member 7 (SLC26A7), coiled-coil domain containing 81 (CCDC81), cadherin 8 (CDH8), family with sequence similarity 124 member A (FAM124A), coiled-coil domain containing 3 (CCDC3), inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain 2 (ITIH2), chondrolectin (CHODL), neural cell adhesion molecule 2 (NCAM2), solute carrier family 26 member 2 (SLC26A2), chloride intracellular channel 2 (CLIC2), glutamate receptor interacting protein 1 (GRIP1), F-box protein 32 (FBXO32), six transmembrane epithelial antigen of the prostate 2 metalloredutase (STEAP2), grainyhead like transcription factor 3 (GRHL3), nucleophosmin/nucleoplasmin 2 (NPM2), chloride intracellular channel 6 (CLIC6), actin alpha cardiac muscle 1 (ACTC1), spondin 2 (SPON2), C3 and PZP like alpha-2-macroglobulin domain containing 8 (CPAMD8), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), AKNA domain containing 1 (AKNAD1), sphingosine-1-phosphate phosphatase 2 (SGPP2), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit gamma 1 (GABRG1), carboxypeptidase A3 (CPA3), neuropeptide Y receptor Y1 (NPY1R), hyperpolarization activated cyclic nucleotide gated potassium channel 1 (HCN1), adenylate cyclase 1 (ADCY1), defensin beta 1 (DEFB1), lysine demethylase 1B (KDM1B), transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 6 (TRPV6), WNK lysine deficient protein kinase 2 (WNK2), aquaporin 3 (Gill blood group) (AQP3), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL), solute carrier family 16 member 9 (SLC16A9), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit beta 2 (CACNB2), coiled-coil domain containing 68 (CCDC68), myosin IA (MYO1A), glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase 1 (GPD1), dynein axonemal assembly factor 3 (DNAAF3), phospholipase A and acyltransferase 5 (HRASLS5), bradykinin receptor B2 (BDKRB2), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein (PHYHIP), neuronal vesicle trafficking associated 1 (NSG1), kallikrein related peptidase 7 (KLK7), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 9 (PCSK9), RAB3B, member RAS oncogene family (RAB3B), mucin 3A, cell surface associated (MUC3A), DLG associated protein 1 (DLGAP1), heparan sulfate 6-O-sulfotransferase 2 (HS6ST2), potassium two pore domain channel subfamily K member 3 (KCNK3), lysophosphatidic acid receptor 3 (LPAR3), anoctamin 5 (ANO5), angiopoietin like 7 (ANGPTL7), tryptase alpha/beta 1 (TPSAB1), cold shock domain containing C2 (CSDC2), radial spoke head component 9 (RSPH9), syntrophin gamma 2 (SNTG2), leucine rich repeat and Ig domain containing 2 (LINGO2), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), myosin ID (MYO1D), LRRN4 C-terminal like (LRRN4CL), reprimin, TP53 dependent G2 arrest mediator homolog (RPRM), transmembrane protein 125 (TMEM125), cadherin 4 (CDH4), transmembrane protein 30B (TMEM30B), synemin (SYNM), receptor interacting serine/threonine kinase 4 (RIPK4), family with sequence similarity 162 member B (FAM162B), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member A3 (ALDH1A3), coiled-coil serine rich protein 1 (CCSER1), brain expressed X-linked 5 (BEX5), oxysterol binding protein 2 (OSBP2), short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family 42E, member 1 (SDR42E1), v-maf avian musculoaponeurotic fibrosarcoma oncogene homolog F (MAFF), RNA binding motif protein 11 (RBM11), limbic system associated membrane protein (LSAMP), potas-

sium voltage-gated channel interacting protein 4 (KCNIP4), piccolo presynaptic cytomatrix protein (PCLO), NF2, moesin-ezrin-radixin like (MERLIN) tumor suppressor (NF2), BCR activator of RhoGEF and GTPase (BCR), metallophosphoesterase domain containing 1 (MPPED1), pyroglutamylated RFamide peptide receptor (QRFPR), FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4), solute carrier family 6 member 9 (SLC6A9), laminin subunit beta 3 (LAMB3), tryptase beta 2 (TPSB2), DDB1 and CUL4 associated factor 12 like 2 (DCAF12L2), SH3 domain binding glutamate rich protein like 2 (SH3BGRL2), chromosome 9 open reading frame 129 (C9orf129) and SEC14 like lipid binding 6 (SEC14L6), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of KLF4 with these genes.

Table 7 and 8 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 9 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 7 and 8. The table 7 and 8 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t KLF4.

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS KLF4									
	RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T KLF4								
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
SLC7A8 - KLF4	156	189	178	44	AFDN - KLF4	211	229	157	11
PIANP - KLF4	210	244	288	152	MAEL - KLF4	292	293	299	241
TUBA4A - KLF4	151	148	176	92	HECW2 - KLF4	204	145	173	202
COL2A1 - KLF4	194	193	284	305	ILDR2 - KLF4	305	307	303	272
GALNT13 - KLF4	223	232	226	292	MGAT3 - KLF4	232	194	250	9
CDKL2 - KLF4	159	202	277	275	MDGA2 - KLF4	288	240	229	204
SUSD4 - KLF4	278	262	269	301	CCDC150 - KLF4	257	153	197	161
LDLR - KLF4	176	109	136	167	EGF - KLF4	252	267	218	254
PRDM16 - KLF4	261	174	185	52	HHIPL2 - KLF4	254	230	264	273
ACK3 - KLF4	154	290	256	188	KIF21A - KLF4	201	154	174	72
SLC44A3 - KLF4	272	216	168	121	THSD7B - KLF4	274	235	234	251
GADL1 - KLF4	275	298	217	270	GABRB2 - KLF4	262	254	268	163
SSC4D - KLF4	234	253	281	180	SLC26A7 - KLF4	294	296	306	286
CCDC81 - KLF4	279	228	211	111	CDH8 - KLF4	253	231	198	120
FAM124A - KLF4	228	222	216	222	CCDC3 - KLF4	212	303	255	227
ITIH2 - KLF4	244	214	257	158	CHODL - KLF4	240	306	248	189
NCAM2 - KLF4	174	256	251	108	SLC26A2 - KLF4	187	286	282	215
CLIC2 - KLF4	166	188	224	51	GRIP1 - KLF4	221	195	207	165
FBXO32 - KLF4	247	300	238	265	STEAP2 - KLF4	289	260	258	122
GRHL3 - KLF4	285	273	181	258	NPM2 - KLF4	152	203	184	118
CLIC6 - KLF4	264	225	146	244	ACTC1 - KLF4	169	237	233	106
SPON2 - KLF4	217	226	192	178	CPAMD8 - KLF4	220	233	230	153
CYP3A4 - KLF4	216	175	149	128	AKNAD1 - KLF4	224	301	290	173
SGPP2 - KLF4	237	210	279	268	GABRG1 - KLF4	293	278	237	216
CPA3 - KLF4	265	200	253	177	NPY1R - KLF4	209	208	302	283
HCN1 - KLF4	286	294	266	300	ADCY1 - KLF4	202	180	169	49
DEFB1 - KLF4	306	305	293	278	KDM1B - KLF4	193	213	193	83
TRPV6 - KLF4	173	192	227	168	WNK2 - KLF4	250	271	276	232
AQP3 - KLF4	259	284	292	280	PHYHIPL - KLF4	296	249	194	194

Table 7: 2nd order interaction ranking between KLF4 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 7 and 8 graphically, with the following influences - ● Individual members w.r.t KLF4 with KLF4 – > SLC7A8 / AFDN /

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS KLF4									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T KLF4									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
SLC16A9 - KLF4	230	275	200	190	CACNB2 - KLF4	162	196	156	69
CCDC68 - KLF4	277	302	304	211	MYO1A - KLF4	182	246	213	135
GPD1 - KLF4	229	247	262	240	DNAAF3 - KLF4	225	227	225	248
HRASLS5 - KLF4	290	245	267	277	BDKRB2 - KLF4	283	287	275	299
PHYHIP - KLF4	298	209	296	281	NSG1 - KLF4	197	199	214	224
KLK7 - KLF4	233	304	297	304	PCSK9 - KLF4	276	239	287	195
RAB3B - KLF4	161	268	270	151	MUC3A - KLF4	304	276	285	284
DLGAP1 - KLF4	255	266	215	231	HS6ST2 - KLF4	270	279	265	228
KCNK3 - KLF4	242	217	272	147	LPAR3 - KLF4	256	265	289	159
ANO5 - KLF4	181	141	240	220	ANGPTL7 - KLF4	199	176	205	207
TPSAB1 - KLF4	248	261	242	155	CSDC2 - KLF4	299	238	232	259
RSPH9 - KLF4	258	166	219	150	SNTG2 - KLF4	297	269	295	289
LINGO2 - KLF4	214	257	291	132	SLCO2A1 - KLF4	269	223	172	209
MYO1D - KLF4	266	285	199	182	LRRN4CL - KLF4	219	156	165	134
RPRM - KLF4	260	250	305	250	TMEM125 - KLF4	184	211	221	154
CDH4 - KLF4	301	224	294	238	TMEM30B - KLF4	218	272	239	169
SYNM - KLF4	207	255	159	185	RIPK4 - KLF4	246	206	273	203
FAM162B - KLF4	185	251	286	143	ALDH1A3 - KLF4	213	220	244	148
CCSER1 - KLF4	190	207	142	109	BEX5 - KLF4	267	289	204	206
OSBP2 - KLF4	235	155	203	174	SDR42E1 - KLF4	263	234	223	144
MAFF - KLF4	188	252	222	137	RBM11 - KLF4	222	169	210	88
LSAMP - KLF4	273	291	263	199	KCNIP4 - KLF4	287	270	274	296
PCLO - KLF4	227	241	189	225	NF2 - KLF4	206	198	153	191
BCR - KLF4	238	185	236	146	MPPED1 - KLF4	268	280	300	213
QRFPR - KLF4	295	283	307	252	FAT4 - KLF4	215	295	180	117
SLC6A9 - KLF4	164	178	187	96	LAMB3 - KLF4	236	248	209	93
TPSB2 - KLF4	281	263	246	149	DCAF12L2 - KLF4	300	288	301	288
SH3BGRL2 - KLF4	200	205	196	80	C9orf129 - KLF4	271	190	261	217
SEC14L6 - KLF4	282	219	271	269					

Table 8: 2nd order interaction ranking between KLF4 VS Individual members.

PIANP / MAEL / TUBA4A / HECW2 / COL2A1 / ILDR2 / GALNT13 / MGAT3 / CDKL2 / MDGA2 / SUSD4 / CCDC150 / LDLR / EGF / PRDM16 / HHIPL2 / ACK3 / KIF21A / SLC44A3 / THSD7B / GADL1 / GABRB2 / SSC4D / SLC26A7 / CCDC81 / CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 / ITIH2 / CHODL / NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 / FBXO32 / STEAP2 / GRHL3 / NPM2 / CLIC6 / ACTC1 / SPON2 / CPAMD8 / CYP3A4 / AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / GABRG1 / CPA3 / NPY1R / HCN1 / ADCY1 / DEFB1 / KDM1B / TRPV6 / WNK2 / AQP3 / PHYHIPL / SLC16A9 / CACNB2 / CCDC68 / MYO1A / GPD1 / DNAAF3 / HRASLS5 / BDKRB2 / PHYHIP / NSG1 / KLK7 / PCSK9 / RAB3B / MUC3A / DLGAP1 / HS6ST2 / KCNK3 / LPAR3 / ANO5 / ANGPTL7 / TPSAB1 / CSDC2 / RSPH9 / SNTG2 / LINGO2 / SLCO2A1 / MYO1D / LRRN4CL / RPRM / TMEM125 / CDH4 / TMEM30B / SYNM / RIPK4 / FAM162B / ALDH1A3 / CCSER1 / BEX5 / OSBP2 / SDR42E1 / MAFF / RBM11 / LSAMP / KCNIP4 / PCLO / NF2 / BCR / MPPED1 / QRFPR / FAT4 / SLC6A9 / LAMB3 / TPSB2 / DCAF12L2 / SH3BGRL2 / C9orf129 and SEC14L6.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Unknown Individual members w.r.t KLF4	
SLC7A8 / AFDN / PIANP / MAEL / TUBA4A ...	
HECW2 / COL2A1 / ILDR2 / GALNT13 / MGAT3 ...	
CDKL2 / MDGA2 / SUSL4 / CCDC150 / LDLR ...	
EGF / PRDM16 / HHIPL2 / ACK3 / KIF21A ...	
SLC44A3 / THSD7B / GADL1 / GABRB2 / SSC4D ...	
SLC26A7 / CCDC81 / CDH8 / FAM124A / CCDC3 ...	
ITIH2 / CHODL / NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 ...	
GRIP1 / FBXO32 / STEAP2 / GRHL3 / NPM2 ...	
CLIC6 / ACTC1 / SPON2 / CPAMD8 / CYP3A4 ...	
AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / GABRG1 / CPA3 / NPY1R ...	
HCN1 / ADCY1 / DEFB1 / KDM1B / TRPV6 ...	
WNK2 / AQP3 / PHYHIPL / SLC16A9 / CACNB2 ...	
CCDC68 / MYO1A / GPD1 / DNAAF3 / HRASLS5 ...	
BDKRB2 / PHYHIP / NSG1 / KLK7 / PCSK9 ...	
RAB3B / MUC3A / DLGAP1 / HS6ST2 / KCNK3 ...	
LPAR3 / ANO5 / ANGPTL7 / TPSAB1 / CSDC2 ...	
RSPH9 / SNTG2 / LINGO2 / SLCO2A1 / MYO1D ...	
LRRN4CL / RPRM / TMEM125 / CDH4 / TMEM30B ...	
SYNM / RIPK4 / FAM162B / ALDH1A3 / CCSER1 ...	
BEX5 / OSBP2 / SDR42E1 / MAFF / RBM11 / LSAMP ...	
KCNIP4 / PCLO / NF2 / BCR / MPPED1 / QRFPR ...	
FAT4 / SLC6A9 / LAMB3 / TPSB2 / DCAF12L2 / ...	
SH3BGRL2 / C9orf129 / SEC14L6	KLF4

Table 9: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between KLF4 and Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic KLF4 2^{nd} order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of KLF4-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

5. References

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